

Review Article

What Causes Gravity?

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Introduction

There seems to be some confusion about Gravity started by Einstein. Gravity is not caused by the bending of space; It is caused by the angular momentum of a spinning electron. The more Mass, the more gravity. This is why Gravity is stronger the closer you are to the Mass. Its also why the more Mass, the more Gravitational pull.

Have you ever tried to life a spinning globe? (I suggest every science teacher do this for his or her students). There is a force in the forearm as one tries to life a spinning globe of the earth on a axis. This is the same conservation of angular momentum that is gravity.

Newton:

$$F=GM$$

$$8/3=(2/3)M$$

$$M=4$$

$$\text{But } M=Ln t$$

$$dM/dt=1/t=1/(1/2)=2$$

Now:

$$\alpha=\omega^2R$$

$$\alpha=(1)^2R$$

$$\alpha=R$$

$$F=\alpha M$$

$$8/3=(RM=\text{Moment}=F \times d$$

$$8/3=8/3 d$$

$$d=1=s=t$$

GMP:

$$t^2-t-1=E$$

$$1-1-1=-1 @t=1/2$$

Momentum

$$P=Mv$$

$$=2(1/\sqrt{2})=\sqrt{2}$$

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$$=\sin 45^\circ+\cos 45^\circ$$

$$P=F+P$$

$$F=0=\sin t$$

$$t=0$$

$$0^2-0-1=-1=E @t=0$$

And,

$$F=\alpha M$$

$$F=RM$$

$$8/3=R (4)$$

$$M=2=dM/dt$$

$$y=y'$$

$$R=2/3=G$$

$$\text{Area}=\pi R^2$$

$$=\pi (2/3)^2$$

$$=13.96$$

$$\text{Circ}=2\pi R=A'$$

$$=2\pi (2/3)$$

$$=4118$$

$$13.96/4.118=0.3333=1/3=1/c=1/t=E$$

From the Periodic Table:

$$F=MG$$

$$(118)(2/3)$$

$$=7866=\pi/4=t$$

$$F=t$$

$$E=1/t=1/F$$

$$F=MG$$

$$=294(2/3)$$

$$=196=\infty$$

196 x 6.022=118.

M x t=E

118.018 x 4.2325=4.997~5=E

There is no need for Einstein's curved space, which makes no sense to me

anyway. The simple explanation of angular momentum of spinning electrons makes perfect sense based on what we know of the macroworld. There are more electrons as we go up the periodic table. More mass; more gravity. As well, the more mass of a substance we have, the stronger the gravitational pull. Finally, gravity is a very weak force because electrons are so small. Everything makes sense with my notion of gravity.

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